

21GRD08 SoMMet

D6: Good practice guide for harmonising soil moisture measurement methods to overcome temporal and spatial differences (lateral scales ranging from point scale to km scale) and the influence of other state variables such as air humidity and soil temperature affecting the measurements

Prepared by: UNIBO and UKCEH

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**METROLOGY
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Deliverable **D6** of project 21GRD08 SoMMet

Good practice guide for harmonising soil moisture measurement methods to overcome temporal and spatial differences (lateral scales ranging from point scale to km scale) and the influence of other state variables such as air humidity and soil temperature affecting the measurements

Authors:

Sadra Emamalizadeh (UNIBO), Tim Howson (UKCEH), Riccardo Mazzoleni (UNIBO), Philip Vincent (UKCEH), Jonathan G. Evans (UKCEH) and Gabriele Baroni (UNIBO)

Institutions:

UNIBO – University of Bologna, Italy

UKCEH – UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology, United Kingdom

Glossary

SWC: Soil water content
PTFs: Pedotransfer functions
RS: Remote sensing
PS: Point-scale
CRNS: Cosmic-ray neutron sensors
WP: Wilting point
FC: Field capacity
R: Correlation coefficient
ubRMSD: Unbiased root mean square deviation
TC: Triple collocation
ML: Machine learning
RF: Random forest
QC: Quality control
TDT: Time domain transmission
VWC: Volumetric water content
SSM: Surface soil moisture
S: Saturation
BD: Bulk density
T: Characteristic time length

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Summary

This document, deliverable D6, is the sixth of eight technical deliverables of the project 21GRD08 SoMMet (hereafter: SoMMet). The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States (Funder name: European Partnership on Metrology; Funder ID: 10.13039/100019599; Grant number: 21GRD08 SoMMet).

This technical report provides a comprehensive overview and structured workflow for harmonizing diverse soil water content (SWC) datasets, ensuring they are meaningfully comparable while preserving their intrinsic characteristics. This is a critical distinction from data fusion, which integrates datasets into a single product. The research evaluates methods for four key harmonization components: unit, temporal, vertical (depth), and lateral spatial harmonization, using data from seven European sites. The analysis employs a physically based evaluation using pedotransfer functions (PTFs) to define plausible SWC ranges.

For unit harmonization, a total water capacity conversion method was preferred over mean-variance matching, as it better preserved the natural variability of the remote sensing (RS) data and resulted in a higher percentage of values within the defined wilting point (WP) and field capacity (FC) thresholds (37.5 % for CRNS reference and 36.5 % for Point-Scale (PS) reference). The temporal harmonization analysis found that both daily averaging and satellite overpass time selection had a negligible impact on SWC data, with changes in the percentage of values within the WP-FC range being near 0 % for CRNS and 16 % for PS. For depth harmonization, a weighted average for PS and an exponential filter for RS were employed, which improved the alignment of RS data with ground measurements ($\Delta R = 0.15$, $\Delta_{ub}RMSD = -0.03$) while somewhat maintaining the physical realism of the datasets.

The study categorizes lateral spatial harmonization methods into four groups: General Statistical, Triple Collocation (TC), Machine Learning (ML), and Spatial Statistical. The choice of method depends on data availability and research goals. While simpler methods like the areal mean are easy to implement with a single PS sensor, they often fail to preserve the distinct signals of CRNS and RS. The triple collocation method provides a more robust, error-aware approach for data-scarce sites, while ML methods like Random Forest (RF) can capture non-linearity but risk overfitting and data fusion. A more spatially faithful method, ordinary kriging, provided the highest quantitative improvements at sites with dense PS networks, with increases of 16.1 % and 30.5 % in the percentage of values within WP-FC thresholds for CRNS and RS, respectively. The report concludes that the optimal harmonization approach is context-dependent, balancing the trade-offs between data availability, interpretability, and the need for statistical and physical consistency.

The materials and results reported in this document have been used to prepare a manuscript that is currently under review. A preprint of the study is available at (Emamalizadeh et al., 2025).

1 Introduction

Soil water content (SWC), or soil moisture, is a fundamental variable in environmental and hydrological sciences. It regulates land-atmosphere interactions, influences agricultural productivity, affects ecosystem health, and is crucial for hydrological modelling and water resource management. Accurate estimation of SWC is challenging due to its high spatial and moderate temporal variability (Mälicke et al. 2020). Different methods have been developed to estimate SWC at various scales, each with distinct advantages and limitations.

SWC measurement techniques can be broadly categorized into three groups based on their spatial coverage: point-scale sensors (PS), cosmic-ray neutron sensing (CRNS), and remote sensing (RS) satellite images (Emamalizadeh et al. 2024). PS sensors provide localized, high-precision measurements but lack extensive coverage. CRNS offers an intermediate-scale solution (Baroni et al. 2018; Zreda et al. 2008), integrating SWC information over a larger footprint (hundreds of meters). RS, on the other hand, provides large-scale observations, enabling regional and global monitoring but often with lower resolution and depth-limited penetration. Given these differences, direct comparisons between datasets obtained from these methods are not straightforward. When using them for validation, merging, or intercomparison studies, harmonization becomes an essential step to ensure consistency and comparability.

Despite its importance, the concept of harmonization has often been used interchangeably with data fusion in the literature. While both share some similarities, a crucial distinction exists. Data fusion typically aims to integrate multiple datasets into a new product, whereas harmonization, as defined in this report, focuses on making datasets more meaningfully comparable while preserving their distinct characteristics. This definition not only provides a structured approach for handling diverse datasets but also helps in method selection. By positioning harmonization as a necessary step after quality control (QC) and before data merging in the workflow, methodologies that significantly alter the nature of the original dataset can be excluded. A structured harmonization approach ensures that datasets are in a comparable format before any merging occurs. For instance, if one dataset is recorded at an hourly interval while another is available in daily aggregates, harmonization would involve converting both to a common temporal resolution. Without such steps, direct comparisons could be misleading.

The objective of this report is to systematically evaluate harmonization techniques and provide recommendations for their use. Harmonization is categorized into four key components with increasing complexity: unit harmonization, temporal harmonization, vertical harmonization (depth adjustment), and lateral spatial harmonization. To ensure a rigorous comparison, a relatively simple approach was adopted, selecting two or more of the most used and relevant methods for each harmonization element. A key element of this strategy is the use of pedotransfer functions (PTFs) (Szabó, Weynants, and Weber 2021) to provide essential soil properties, such as wilting point (WP) and field capacity (FC), which define the expected range of SWC variations. The impact of

harmonization is then assessed by analysing the percentage of data points falling within these thresholds before and after harmonization, alongside statistical comparisons between datasets.

2 Review the existing soil moisture harmonization methods

2.1 Study Sites and Datasets

The analysis was conducted across seven European sites (Figure 1), primarily affiliated with the SoMMet project (<https://www.sommet-project.eu>) and the COSMOS-UK network (<https://cosmos.ceh.ac.uk>). The sites were selected to represent a range of soil types, land uses, and data availability scenarios, reflecting real-world conditions where data can be sparse and heterogeneous.

UK Sites (Euston, Waddesdon, Hillsborough (Cooper et al. 2021)): Provided the longest and most continuous data records, spanning from 2016 to 2024.

Italian and Czech Sites (Bondeno, Imola, Nucice (Li et al. 2021)): Offered shorter data records with considerable gaps.

Marquadt Site (Germany (Heistermann et al. 2023)): Featured a very dense network of 30 PS sensors but provided only daily CRNS data; it was therefore included only in the vertical and lateral spatial harmonization analysis.

Figure 1. Left panel: Geographic locations of the seven study sites across Europe. Right Panel: Example from the Imola site showing the 1 km RS pixel (grid with black segments), CRNS location and its considered footprint (125 m radius, orange point and grey shaded circle), and PS location (green point). This illustrates the spatial relationship among sensing systems.

2.2 Dataset Descriptions and Pre-processing

1. PS Sensors

- Technology: Mostly static time domain transmission (TDT) sensors.
- Measurement: Highly localized SWC at different depths (typically sensors include depth of 5 cm).
- Processing: Sub-hourly data were aggregated to hourly resolution. All data are in volumetric water content (VWC, m^3/m^3). For the analysis, which required only one sensor, the one closest to the CRNS station was selected.
- Quality Control (QC): Values exceeding $0.6 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$ or equal to zero were removed as outliers (Dorigo et al. 2013).

2. CRNS

- Technology: Measures fast neutrons from cosmic rays moderated by hydrogen (primarily in water).
- Measurement: Integrates SWC over a large area (~5 hectares, 125 m radius) with a depth sensitivity that is highest at the surface.
- Processing: Pre-processed (corrected for pressure, humidity, and neutron flux) hourly data in VWC were obtained from site operators.
- QC: The same outlier filter as for PS data was applied.
- RS Product
- Product: Copernicus Sentinel-1 Surface Soil Moisture (SSM) product (<https://land.copernicus.eu/>) (Bauer-Marschallinger et al. 2019).
- Technology: C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (C-SAR) measuring surface dielectric properties.
- Measurement: Daily SSM at 1 km resolution for the top few cm (<5 cm) of soil, provided in relative saturation (S, 0-100 %).

- Processing: The pixel covering each CRNS station was extracted. QC was applied after unit conversion to VWC.

2.3 Unit Harmonization

The harmonization process was executed in a sequential manner, with multiple methods evaluated for each dimension of scale mismatch.

The Copernicus RS product provides data in S, while ground data are in VWC. Two conversion methods were applied and compared.

1. Total Water Capacity Method (Physical): Converts S to VWC using soil hydraulic properties (Genuchten 1980).

$$\theta = S \cdot (\phi - WP) + WP$$

- Parameters: Porosity (ϕ) was derived from SoilGrids bulk density (BD) data ($\phi = 1 - BD/2.65$ (Saxton and Rawls 2006)). WP was estimated from the minimum hourly ground observation. The maximum ground observation (if greater than ϕ) was used as the upper bound.
 - Strengths: Physically interpretable, preserves RS dynamics.
 - Weaknesses: Highly dependent on the accuracy of soil input maps.
2. Mean-Variance Matching Method (Statistical): Statistically aligns the RS data to the ground reference.
 - Strengths: Does not require soil data, ensures statistical alignment.
 - Weaknesses: Alters the natural mean and variability of the RS signal.
 - Each method was applied using both PS and CRNS as the reference, resulting in four harmonized RS datasets for subsequent analysis.

2.4 Temporal Harmonization

PS and CRNS provide hourly data, while RS is daily. Two methods were used to align the temporal scales.

1. Daily Averaging: Hourly ground data were aggregated into daily mean values.

- Strengths: Uses all available data, smooths noise, suitable for long-term studies.
 - Weaknesses: Obscures short-term dynamics (e.g., irrigation, diurnal cycles).
2. Satellite Overpass Selection: Hourly ground data corresponding to the exact Sentinel-1 overpass times (05:00/17:00 UTC for Italian/Czech sites, 06:00/18:00 UTC for UK sites) were selected.
- Strengths: Provides a direct point-to-point comparison for validation.
 - Weaknesses: Discards most of the data, reducing statistical power.

Disaggregation methods were explicitly excluded to avoid generating synthetic data.

2.5 Depth Harmonization

The sensors have different effective sensing depths: RS (0-5 cm), PS (5 cm), and CRNS (integrated, sensitive to ~0-50 cm). Two strategies were employed.

1. No Adjustment (Direct Comparison): Datasets were compared directly. This approach is justified by the strong surface sensitivity of CRNS and the relevance of surface SWC for many applications. It is simple and preserves original data integrity.
2. Weighted Averaging and Exponential Filtering: A more physical approach to align datasets with the CRNS depth sensitivity.
 - PS Adjustment: Where multiple PS sensors at different depths were available, a weighted average was computed using a physics-based depth weighting function (Schrön et al. 2017) that accounts for neutron attenuation.
 - RS Adjustment: An exponential filter (Wagner, Lemoine, and Rott 1999) was applied to the RS time series to simulate the damping and lagging of the surface signal as it propagates downward. The filter parameter (T) was optimized for each site to maximize agreement with ground data.

2.7 Lateral Spatial Harmonization

A literature review of 35 studies identified five categories of methods. Based on data availability and the study's philosophy, one method from each applicable category was selected for implementation (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Frequency of five lateral spatial harmonization categories in the literature review: general statistical, machine learning, triple collocation, spatial statistical, and process-based. Percentages indicate each method's share of the total.

- General Statistical - Areal Mean: PS values within a footprint (CRNS or RS) were arithmetically averaged. This simple method relies on the temporal stability concept.
- Triple Collocation: The error variances of PS, CRNS, and RS were estimated using triple collocation. The dataset with the lowest error was then used as a reference for mean-variance matching of the other two (Gruber et al. 2013; Stoffelen 1998).
- Machine Learning - Random Forest (RF): RF was used for both upscaling (PS to CRNS scale) and downscaling (RS to CRNS scale), using distance-weighted sensors as predictors.
- Spatial Statistics - Ordinary Kriging: This geostatistical interpolation technique was applied only at Bondeno and Marquadt due to their sufficient number of PS sensors required for stable variogram modelling.
- Process-Based Models: These were reviewed but not implemented, as they generate fully synthetic time series, conflicting with the study's objective of harmonizing original sensor data.

Table 1: Overview of lateral spatial harmonization methods with key features, strengths, and limitations to support method selection.

Category	Example Methods	Statistical or Physical	Spatial Awareness	PS Sensors Needed	Ease of Implementation	Strengths	Limitations
General Statistics	OLS, Ridge Regression, Arithmetic Mean	Statistical	Low	1 or more	Easy	Simple, fast, low data needs	Assumes linearity, limited spatial adaptation
Machine Learning	RF, kNN, SVM, NN	Statistical	Medium	Several	Moderate to Hard	Captures non-linearity, handles large variability	Data-hungry, opaque, may shift SWC patterns
Triple Collocation	Standard TC, Extended TC (Yuan et al. 2020)	Statistical	Low	1 or more	Moderate	Error decomposition without a reference	Requires 3 datasets, dependent on assumption validity
Spatial Statistics	Kriging, Variogram analysis	Statistical	High	Several	Moderate	Honors spatial autocorrelation, well-suited for mapping	Needs a dense PS network, sensitive to spatial assumptions
Process-Based Models	HYDRUS-1D, JULES	Physical	Medium to High	Not Needed	Hard	Physically meaningful, rich simulation capability	Data-intensive, parameter uncertainty, and computational cost

2.8 Evaluation Metrics and Pedotransfer Functions

PTFs: The “euptfv2” model (<https://ptfinterface.rissac.hu>) (Szabó et al. 2021) was used with SoilGrids (<https://soilgrids.org>) texture data to estimate FC and WP for 0-5 cm, 0-15 cm, and 0-30 cm depth ranges (Poggio et al. 2021). These thresholds provided a physically meaningful framework to assess the plausibility of harmonized SWC values by calculating the percentage of data points falling within the expected range (WP to FC).

Statistical Metrics: Two metrics were used to quantify agreement between datasets:

- Pearson Correlation Coefficient (R): Measures the strength and direction of linear covariation.
- Unbiased Root Mean Square Deviation (ubRMSD): Measures the average magnitude of random error between datasets, removing the effect of systematic bias.

2.9 Overall Workflow

The harmonization process followed a structured workflow (Figure 3). For a given analysis, the appropriate methods from each dimension (unit, temporal, depth, spatial) were selected and applied sequentially. The output was a set of harmonized time series from all three sensor types, allowing for a consistent and multi-faceted evaluation of SWC dynamics across scales. Performance was assessed by comparing the change in PTF-based plausibility and statistical metrics before and after applying each harmonization step.

Figure 3: Workflow of the harmonization process for RS, CRNS, and PS SWC time series. The process includes four main steps: unit conversion, temporal matching, depth adjustment, and lateral spatial harmonization; each with two or more method options. The final outputs are harmonized time series across all sensor types.

3 Application and test of various harmonization approaches

3.1 Unit Harmonization

The performance of two unit-harmonization methods for converting RS saturation data to VWC was evaluated. The total water capacity method (Method 1), which uses soil physical properties (porosity and WP), outperformed the mean-variance matching method (Method 2).

- Performance: Method 1 resulted in a higher percentage (avg. ~37 %) of RS data points falling within the physically plausible range between WP and FC. Method 2 showed lower performance (avg. ~32 %), primarily because its statistical scaling often shifted values below the WP threshold.
- Metrics: While the R remained unchanged (as both methods involve scaling), the ubRMSD showed a slightly better improvement (more negative delta) for Method 1.
- Conclusion: Method 1 is preferred due to its stronger physical basis and better preservation of the RS signal's natural variability. The RS data converted using Method 1 with CRNS as a reference were selected for subsequent analysis.

3.2 Temporal Harmonization

The impact of aligning high-frequency ground data (hourly) with the daily RS product was tested using two methods: selecting values at satellite overpass times (Method 1) and calculating a daily average (Method 2).

- Performance: Both methods yielded nearly identical results. The percentage of ground data within the WP-FC range was virtually unchanged for CRNS and showed a consistent ~16% change for PS across both methods.
- Reasoning: This is attributed to the high "memory" of SWC, meaning it changes slowly over short periods. A single daily value, whether a specific timestamp or an average, effectively represents the day's condition.
- Conclusion: The choice of temporal harmonization method has a negligible effect on outcomes. The daily averaging method (Method 2) was selected for its simplicity and because it utilizes all available data, making it the input for further steps.

3.3 Depth Harmonization

Two strategies were compared: no adjustment (Method 1) and a physics-based adjustment using a weighted average for PS and an exponential filter for RS (Method 2) to align with CRNS depth sensitivity.

- Performance: Method 2 had a negligible effect on PS data but significantly improved the RS data, increasing the percentage of plausible values by ~12 % and improving correlation ($\Delta R = 0.15$) with ground data.
- Effectiveness: The exponential filter successfully smoothed high-frequency noise in the RS signal, making its dynamics more representative of root-zone processes and better aligned with CRNS and PS observations. The optimal filter parameter (characteristic time length T) averaged ~6 days across sites, reflecting the SWC memory effect.
- Conclusion: Method 2 is preferred as it provides a more physically meaningful basis for comparison by accounting for vertical sensitivity differences. Its output was used for the spatial harmonization step.

3.4 Lateral Spatial Harmonization

Four methods were evaluated to reconcile data from different spatial footprints. Their performance was highly dependent on the number of available PS sensors.

A. Methods Feasible with a Single PS Sensor

1. Areal Mean: This simple averaging method led to a -6 % reduction in plausible values for CRNS. While it reduced ubRMSD, it did so by effectively replacing the unique CRNS and RS signals with a PS-based average, erasing their distinctive information.
2. Triple Collocation with Mean-Variance Matching: This method identified the lowest random error sensor (PS in 3 sites, CRNS in 5 sites) and scaled the others to match it. It slightly improved the plausibility for PS and CRNS (+1 %) but reduced it for RS (-5 %). It effectively reduced random error (ubRMSD) without altering R, providing a robust statistical harmonization.

B. Methods Requiring Multiple PS Sensors

1. Random Forest: This machine learning method showed strong statistical improvement (ΔR up to 0.54 for RS). However, it risked overfitting, as the harmonized output closely mimicked the CRNS signal, blurring the line between harmonization and data fusion and losing independent sensor characteristics.

2. Ordinary Kriging: Applied only at Bondeno and Marquadt (8+ sensors), this geostatistical method yielded the best results, increasing plausible values by 16% (CRNS) and 31 % (RS) and significantly improving R. However, it also replaced the original CRNS/RS signals with a PS-based estimate and required long, concurrent data records.

Overall Conclusion on Spatial Harmonization: The optimal method is contingent on data availability. For sites with only one PS sensor, triple collocation provides the most statistically robust approach. For sites with a dense network of sensors, ordinary kriging is the superior choice, offering the greatest improvement by explicitly modelling spatial variability. The areal mean, while simple, is the least effective, and RF, while powerful, may overfit and reduce physical interpretability.

General Statistical - Areal Mean of PS within footprints at Euston site

(a)

Triple Collocation + Mean and Variance Matching at Euston site

(b)

Figure 4: Figures of lateral spatial harmonization methods before and after harmonization. (a) General statistical approach using the areal mean of Point Sensors (PS) within CRNS footprints at the Euston site. (b) Triple Collocation with mean and variance matching at the Euston site. (c) Machine Learning approach using Random Forest for upscaling PS and downscaling Remote Sensing (RS) data at the Euston site. (d) Spatial statistical approach using Ordinary Kriging of PS sensors at the Bondeno site.

Machine Learning - Random Forest for upscaling PS and downscaling RS at Euston site

(c)

Spatial Statistical - Kriging of PS sensors at Bondeno site

(d)

Figure 5 (cont.): Figures of lateral spatial harmonization methods before and after harmonization. (a) General statistical approach using the areal mean of Point Sensors (PS) within CRNS footprints at the Euston site. (b) Triple Collocation with mean and variance matching at the Euston site. (c) Machine Learning approach using Random Forest for upscaling PS and downscaling Remote Sensing (RS) data at the Euston site. (d) Spatial statistical approach using Ordinary Kriging of PS sensors at the Bondeno site.

4 Conclusions

This study demonstrated a structured, multi-step workflow to harmonize soil water content (SWC) data from point-scale sensors (PS), cosmic-ray neutron sensors (CRNS), and remote sensing (RS), making them meaningfully comparable while preserving their distinct characteristics. The process systematically addressed the four fundamental scale mismatches between these datasets.

For unit harmonization, the conversion of the RS product from relative saturation to volumetric water content was most effectively achieved through a physically based method reliant on soil properties like porosity and wilting point, which proved superior to a statistical mean-variance matching approach by better preserving the intrinsic variability of the RS signal.

The temporal alignment of high-frequency ground data with the daily RS product revealed that the slow-changing "memory" of SWC meant both daily averaging and selection based on satellite overpass times performed equally well, with daily averaging chosen for subsequent steps due to its comprehensive use of available data.

The next step was depth adjustment, where a physics-informed strategy employing a weighted average for PS data and an exponential filter for RS data was preferred over a simple direct comparison. This step was essential for creating a physically coherent alignment with the CRNS sensing depth and resulted in a significant improvement, particularly for the RS data.

Finally, the choice of a method for lateral spatial harmonization was shown to be highly contingent upon data availability and specific research objectives. For sites with only a single PS sensor, the Triple Collocation technique combined with mean-variance matching provided a robust statistical foundation by objectively identifying the most reliable dataset for scaling. In contrast, for locations with a dense network of PS sensors, ordinary kriging emerged as the superior option, delivering the greatest improvements by explicitly modelling spatial variability, though it demands extensive sensor coverage and concurrent data records. While machine learning methods like Random Forest showed potential, they carried a risk of overfitting, and simple areal averaging was confirmed as the least effective approach.

The overarching conclusion is that there is no single universal solution for harmonization. Instead, a successful strategy requires the careful selection of the most appropriate tool for each harmonization step, dictated by the available data. The most reliable and rigorous framework for integrating multi-scale SWC data involves employing a physics-based unit conversion, straightforward daily temporal aggregation, essential depth adjustment, and a spatially aware method such as kriging for dense networks or Triple Collocation for sparse ones. This foundational approach significantly enhances the usability and reliability of integrated SWC data for a wide range of hydrological and environmental monitoring applications.

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